

Clim4vitis

Climate change impact mitigation
for European viticulture

CLIM4VITIS DAYS

18-20 February 2019

UTAD, Vila Real

CLIM4VITIS INTRODUCTION

Clim4Vitis is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, funded by the European Commission under the Twinning instrument of the Horizon 2020 Programme. The project aims to promote knowledge transfer and science and technology (S&T) capacity building in viticulture & climate. Clim4Vitis will devise new methods and tools for modelling grapevines, and for assessing climate change impacts on European viticulture. It will lead to increases in UTAD's capability to address such aspects.

GRAPEVINE MODELLING WORKSHOP

CLIM4VITIS CONFERENCE

CLIMATE CHANGE VITICULTURE COURSE

JOIN US!

REGISTER NOW FOR FREE

www.clim4vitis.eu/event/clim4vitisweek/

More info:

www.clim4vitis.eu

www.researchgate.net/project/Clim4Vitis-H2020-Twinning

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GRAPEVINE MODELLING WORKSHOP

This workshop will provide an overview of different state-of-the-art approaches for modelling grapevines. It will be held in four modules, organized by three leading institutions, and will provide insights on elements such as grapevine phenology, growth, yields or pests and diseases under different environmental conditions. A final discussion panel will enable an active participation of all attendees.

Target audience: UTAD's researchers, researchers from partner institutions, relevant individuals from partner universities, winemaking companies and associations.

CLIM4VITIS CONFERENCE

An official launch conference will be organised to disseminate useful insights on the objectives of the project and the impacts foreseen. Distinguished speakers will present their viewpoints on climate change and its potential impacts on European viticulture. This event will be a platform for stakeholders to connect with the project and amongst themselves with a common objective of promoting knowledge transfer and S&T capacity building.

Target audience: Winemaking companies, clusters and associations, viticulture research academia, municipalities, and media groups.

CLIMATE CHANGE VITICULTURE COURSE

This course will be devoted to climate change and European viticulture. It will provide insights on the state-of-the-art and best practices with added value to the sector. To be conducted in three sessions, it will provide not only key knowledge to students and researchers, but also useful information to stakeholders.

Target audience: UTAD post-graduate students, UTAD teaching and research staff, relevant partner institutions and other scientific actors.

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AGENDA

Laboratories Building - B0.01

UTAD, Vila Real

18 FEB

Grapevine Modelling Workshop

15:00 – 15:30

Registration

15:30 – 17:00

Living with Climate Change? Current and expected impacts on European viticulture

Christoph Menz and Thomas Kartschall from PIK, Germany

17:00 – 17:30

Coffee Break

17:30 – 19:00

Modelling grape phenology and yield

Daniel Molitor from LIST, Luxembourg

19 FEB

Grapevine Modelling Workshop

8:30 – 9:00

Registration

9:00 – 10:30

Modelling strategies for estimating vine development and growth

Luisa Leolini, Paolo Merante, Marco Bindi and Marco Moriondo from UNIFI, Italy

10:30 – 11:00

Coffee Break

11:00 – 12:30

Discussion & Closure

Clim4Vitis Conference

14:00 – 14:30

Registration

14:30 – 14:45

Opening session

António Fontainhas Fernandes, UTAD rector

14:45 – 15:00

Overview of Clim4Vitis

João Santos Clim4Vitis Coordinator from UTAD, Portugal

15:00 – 16:00

Invited Keynote Speakers

Hans Schultz from Geisenheim University, Germany
José Roquette from Esporão, Portugal

16:00 – 16:30

Coffee Break

16:30 – 17:30

Invited Keynote Speakers

Benjamin Bois from University of Burgundy, France
Inaki Cortazar from INRA, France

17:30 – 18:00

Closing Cocktail

20 FEB

Climate Change Viticulture Course

8:30 – 9:00

Registration

9:00 – 9:30

Climate change and European viticulture

Christoph Menz and Thomas Kartschall from PIK, Germany

9:30 – 10:00

An overview on climate change effects on viticulture

Paolo Merante, Luisa Leolini, Marco Bindi and Marco Moriondo from UNIFI, Italy

10:00 – 10:30

Impact of climate change on viticulture in Luxembourg

Daniel Molitor and Jürgen Junk from LIST, Luxembourg

10:30 – 11:00

Discussion